

Repositioning of Welding and Fabrication Teaching personnel's Competence in Government Interventionist programs for Vocational Skills and Economic Development of Niger Delta Region

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Abstract

The study tends to reposition welding and fabrication teaching personnel's competence in government interventionist programs for better vocational skills and economic development of the Niger Delta people. To accomplish this, the study adopted descriptive survey design. One RQ and one HO were formulated. The study was carried out in the nine states that make up the Niger Delta region: Abia, Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo, Imo, Ondo and Rivers. The population for the study was 759 respondents comprising: Heads of Training Centers (HTC), Welding Teaching Personnel (WTP), and trainees. 314 respondents were sampled through multi stage sampling techniques. The questionnaire was the data collection instrument; and was validated by three Experts. The reliability co-efficient of the instrument was ascertained to be 0.86. The administration of the instrument was done by the researcher with the help of four research assistants. The mean and standard deviation was used to answer the RQ, while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the HO at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that certified international welders were used for teaching practical; and to a high extent welding teachers show good communication skills, and industrial field experience during teaching. Also, the HO was accepted indicating there is no significant difference in the mean responses of the respondents on the extent to which welding teaching personnel's competence at the centers meet IIW requirements to drive vocational skills. Based on this, the following recommendations amongst others were proffered; welding teaching personnel that possess prerequisite requirements should be sponsored by government interventionist agency (NDDC) to further enhance new knowledge; workshops and seminars on how to run the program to suit IIW standards for vocational skill and economic development of the Niger Delta region should be jointly organized by the stakeholders.

Key Words: Welding and Fabrication Personnel' Competence, Government Interventionist Programs, Vocational Skills

INTRODUCTION

The Niger Delta region is the area covered by the natural delta of the Niger River. It comprises of the following states: Abia, Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo, Imo, Ondo and Rivers. The region contributes about 90% to Nigeria's foreign exchange, earnings and about 85% of federal government revenue, as her economy is largely dependent on the oil and gas deposits in the region (Okolie-Osemene & Okanume, 2012). In spite of the region's huge economic contribution to Nigeria's federation, the state of infrastructural and human capital developments in the region has been very poor. Pollution of the environment that is usually associated with exploration and exploitation activities of oil and gas companies in the region, has impacted negatively on the employment and economic status of the people of the region. This is because the qualities of their farmlands and fishing waters which are their traditional sources of employment and livelihood have been reduced as a result of pollution. These situations have ensued high level of unemployment and poverty among the people, leaving them frustrated in a state of disillusion and hopelessness. The frustration has often pushed the people, especially the youths to restiveness such as oil pipelines vandalisms, and kidnappings

(Chukwezi, 2009). The federal government introduced several interventionist programs to solve this problem.

The federal government now uses different ministries, agencies, and parastatal such as: Ministry of Niger Delta Affairs (MINDA), Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC), and National Directorate of Employment (NDE) to run vocational skills and other economic development programs in the region. These agencies provide vocational skills training in trade areas like welding and fabrication. This they do as a 'quick-fix' solution to the massive unemployment and poverty among the teaming youths of the region which many believe is fueling the restiveness. Through their various vocational skills development programs, they aimed to provide unemployed Niger delta youths with requisite vocational skills to make them employable in related job placements.

Vocational skills are acquired knowledge in a specific trade. This in line with the definition of study.com, (2008) that vocational skills are skills one gains toward becoming knowledgeable in a specific trade or profession. Study.com also asserts that vocational skills are practical or first-hand skills that help a person master

a trade or a job. Study.com further explains that vocational skills can be obtained through hands-on-experience on the job, as well as at vocational school. Common trade areas in which skills are taught at vocational skills development centers across the Niger Delta region include: welding and fabrication, plant repairs, refrigeration and air-conditioning which are classified under mechanical business skills. Others are hair dressing, fashion designing and tailoring, soap making and cosmetology, catering and restaurant management classified under home management business skills.

Welding, as defined by Larry, (2011), is a fabrication or sculptural process that joins material, usually metals or thermoplastics by causing coalescence. Also, Lippolds (2011) defined welding as the process of joining together pieces of metals, so that bonding accompanied by appreciable inter-atomic penetration takes place at the original boundary surfaces. Welding is carried out by the use of heat or pressure or both and with or without added metal. The major types of welding processes include: electric arc, gas, metal arc, and resistance welding. These welding types have wide applications in various engineering and technology fields.

Among the trade areas welding and fabrication stands out as one that can have positive significant impact on the employment and poverty situation of the people of the region. This is because the labor needs in this area is always in high demand since it is the major technological activity of the oil and gas companies and allied industries operating in the region and worldwide. This is in line with the assertion of IIW-India, (2009) that welding professionals have become a “precious commodity” all over the world because of the increasing growth in welding activities around the world. For instance, the number of welders and fitters needed for the fabrication, installation and periodic maintenance of pipes and other components in the ongoing National Integrated Power Project and the West African Gas Pipeline Project can best be imagined. Moreover, the Nigerian local content Act (2010) mandates oil and gas companies in Nigeria to give preferences to Nigerians, especially Niger Deltas’ whenever employment opportunities exist in their companies (NDDC, 2012). Also, the re-numeration for a skilled International Welder (IW), which is the minimum national welding skill requirement for a welder to be employed in oil and gas industry, and is the least cadre is

about ₦360,000 monthly (NIWELFU, 2012). For welders who might be self-employed, there are enormous opportunities because of the increasing demand for metal burglary proofs, doors and windows, both for residential and industrial buildings. Developing welding and fabrication skills in the teeming youths is, therefore, one sure way to reduce unemployment and poverty levels, and their attendant consequences of restiveness in the region.

Welding and Fabrication do not exactly mean the same thing in the fields of engineering and technology, although they are strongly related in definitions and uses. Fabrication, according to Arora, (2004) is the manufacture of parts, usually structural or electromechanical parts. It involves the assembly of parts into a structure. Classes of fabrication include: metal, wood, and plastic fabrication depending on the material used in the process. For the purpose of this study, the researcher’s focus is on metal fabrication; because it is the major class of fabrication that is dominant in the oil and gas industry in the Niger Delta region. Metal fabrication according to Arora, (2004) is the building of metal structures by Cutting, Bending and Assembly processes. Assembly simply means joining of pieces. Welding is one of the joining processes of Assembly, whereas, Assembly is one of the stages of fabrication.

To produce the International Welders, who should be competent, it is therefore, not enough to run welding and fabrication skills training program; but the program should be run in line with international standards and best practices such as provided for by requirements of International Institute of Welding (IIW). IIW is the universally recognized organization that provides standards and guidelines in terms of curricula, facilities, personnel, examinations and qualifications, and other welding practices (IIW, 2011). For the purpose of this study, the researcher’s focus is on standard requirement visa vis the competence of Welding Teaching Personnel (WTP) involved in the welding and fabrication skills training program. By IIW requirement, two categories of WTP should be involved in the training. The category that teaches theory, called welding teacher, should be a certified International Welding Technologist (IWT), while the category that teach practical, called welding instructor should be a certified International Welder (IW) (EWF-IIW, 2004). It is also required that the welding teacher possess good verbal communication skill,

demonstrate competence, and be in touch with the industry. Welding teaching personnel that meet these requirements can be said to be competent.

Competence is a combination of practical and theoretical knowledge, cognitive skills, behavior and values used to improve performance in welding and fabrication technology; or as the state or quality of being adequately or well qualified, having the ability to perform a specific role. Competency is also used as a more general description of the requirements of human beings in organizations and communities. It is within the context of these definitions and views that welding teaching personnel's competence in welding and fabrication skills training programs in the Niger Delta region will bring about good economic fortune.

In the opinion of Random (2015) personnel is defined as body of persons employed in an organization or place of work. In the context of this study, welding and fabrication personnel are those employed in the organization to carry out the duties of joining, and forming metals piece together to produce certain part or component. However, personnel cannot be productive if he or she is not qualified or/competent. According to EWF-IIW, (2004), high and equal level of qualification of welding personnel is a fundamental pre-requisite for ensuring the quality requirements of welders in all member countries of the European Federation for welding, joining and cutting. Welding Teaching Personnel, according to EWF-IIW, (2004) are classified into two - Welding Teacher for teaching of theoretical modules, and welding instructors for teaching of the practical modules; training coordinators are the head of training centers.

The need to carry out repositioning research on welding teaching personnel's competence in welding and fabrication skills training programs in the Niger Delta region was born out of the reality that programs have had little or no impact on the general attitude of the youths and their employment status. This is because, according to Nigeria Welders and Fitters Union (NIWELFU) (2012), NDDC-trained welders are currently, not employed as welders in the oil and gas companies in the region to the knowledge of the union, though they do apply. NIWELFU further noted that if NDDC which is the most funded, and organized with so much regional and political influence, compared to other government ministries, agencies and parastatals in turning out

granddaunts that are below standard, needless to talk of others. NIWELFU however pointed out that their welders are sometimes engaged in oil and gas companies in their states, local government areas and communities of origin, not as welders, but as helpers, in order to quell community threats, and generally pacify Niger Delta youths to build vocational skills that will bring about economic development of the region.

Statement of the Problem

Welding and fabrication skill acquisition programs, like that of NDDC, were instituted to inculcate in the beneficiaries requisite welding and fabrication skills for the attainment of the minimum national welding skill requirements that would make them employable and be effectively utilized in the oil and gas industry, where labor needs for trained welders, is always in high demand. This is with a view to empowering the people economically and stemming the tide of restiveness in the region.

In spite of the existence of the program for over ten years, graduates of the program have not been able to gain the needed employment as welders in the oil and gas industry. According to Nigerian Welders and Fitters Union (NIWELFU), (2012), graduates of the NDDC welding and fabrication skill acquisition program are not employed as welders in oil and gas industry in Nigeria because they are not registered with the union. According to NIWELFU, (2012), graduates of the program are not registered with the union because none of them met the national minimum welding skill requirement for employment in oil and gas industry neither were they are able to pass required tests (Aptitude tests in Modules A, B & C) that covers trainings for International Welder, which is a major criterion for a welder to be registered with the union. It follows, therefore, that the quality of graduates of the programs is low, and by extension, the quality of the programs is low. This has negated the realization of their objectives, especially in terms of addressing unemployment situation and its attendant consequences of militancy that has continued to ravage the region. There is therefore, a missing link and state of affair that is not satisfactory. The low quality of the program could be as a result of low adherence to international best practices as provided for by standards and requirements of International Institute of Welding (IIW), particularly in the area of welding teaching personnel. This is in line with the assertion of Aremu, (1987) that the success of any program is largely determined by the objectives of the

program, the provision of instructional facilities, fund, instructional materials, well defined curriculum content, in addition to well-motivated students and class room teachers. This has informed the researcher to ask this question: Are the programs run in line with international best practices as provided for by the standards and requirements of International Institute of Welding, in terms of the welding teaching personnel's competence? One of the ways of providing answers that will address the problems of vocational skills and economic development of the people of Niger Delta region is to reposition welding and fabrication technology teaching personnel's competence. Non-repositioning of welding and fabrication technology teaching personnel's competence, has created information and knowledge gap as a problem this study intends to fill. It is on the basis of these that repositioning research on welding and fabrication technology teaching personnel's competence becomes imperative to guide in decision making to better vocational skills and economic development in the region.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was "repositioning of welding and fabrication technology teaching personnel's competence in government interventionist programs for vocational skills and economic development of the Niger Delta region". The specific objective was to ascertain:

1. The extent to which welding and fabrication teaching personnel at interventionist training centers meet IIW requirements for vocational skill and economic development of the Niger Delta region.

Research Question

RQ₁: To what extent does welding and fabrication teaching personnel's competence at Government interventionist training centers meet IIW requirements for vocational skill and economic development of the Niger Delta region?

Hypothesis

H₀1: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of the respondents on the extent to which welding and fabrication teaching personnel's competence at government interventionist training centers meet IIW requirements for vocational skill and economic development of the Niger Delta region.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a descriptive survey research design. The study was carried out in the Niger Delta region (Abia, Akwa-Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo, Imo, Ondo and Rivers) of Nigeria. The total population for this study was 748 respondents from the training centers of the interventionist agency Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC) across the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. They are distributed as follows: 700 trainees, 37 welding and fabrication teaching personnel and 11 heads of training centers/coordinators. The distribution of 748 respondents according to states training centers are as thus: Abia-27, Akwa-Ibom- 163, Bayelsa-76, Cross-River-19, Delta-142, Edo-28, Imo-26, Ondo-47, and Rivers-220. (Source: Commercial and Industrial Development Directorate, NDDC Headquarters, Port Harcourt, Staff print-out 2016). The final sample size for the study was found to be 303. It comprised 255 Trainees, 37 Welding Teaching Personnel (WTP) and 11 Heads of Training Centers/Coordinators. The breakdown of the sample size according to States shows that there are 12 respondents from Abia (8 Trainees, 3 WTP, 1 HTC), 63 respondents from Akwa-Ibom (58 Trainees, 4 WTP, 1 HTC), 30 respondents from Bayelsa (26 Trainees, 3 WTP, 1 HTC), 9 respondents from Cross-River (6 Trainees, 2 WTP, 1 HTC), 55 respondents from Delta (49 Trainees, 5 WTP, 1 HTC), 13 respondents from Edo (9 Trainees, 3 WTP, 1 HTC), 11 respondents from Imo (8 Trainees, 2 WTP, 1 HTC), 19 respondents from Ondo (16 Trainees, 2 WTP, 1 HTC), and 91 respondents from Rivers (75 Trainees, 13 WTP, 3 HTC).

Multistage sampling technique was adopted in determining the sample size for the study. Multistage sampling was used because there are different stages involved in selecting the sample of the categories of respondents. At the first stage, to determine the sample size of trainees Taro Yamani (1964) formula was used which yielded a sample size of 255. To select the 255 trainees, proportionate sampling technique was used to arrive at the real numbers of the trainees per center by determining the percentage of trainees to be selected from each center. The choice for proportionate sampling is because of the different population at the training centers. Random sampling by balloting was used to select the trainees unbiased. At the second stage, the population of the other categories of respondents (WTP and HTC) was all used because of their manageable sizes.

The instrument that was used for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled “Repositioning of Welding and Fabrication Teaching Personnel’s Competence on vocational Skill Training Programs in Niger Delta region (WFTPCVSP). A 4-point scale on a weighted value of 4 – 1 was adopted for the response options. The response options and their weights are: VHE: Very High Extent- 4, HE: High Extent- 3, LE: Low Extent- 2, and VLE: Very Low Extent- 1. The instrument was subjected to face validation by giving it to three experts; two from Department of Industrial Technical Education, Faculty of Vocational and Technical Education; and one from Department of Science Education (Measurement and Evaluation Unit), Faculty of Education all in University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Comments and suggestions by these experts helped in modifying the items to suit the purpose of the study.

The reliability of the instrument was determined by administering copies of the questionnaire to 25 respondents. The responses of the respondents were subjected to reliability analysis using Cronbach Alpha to determine the internal consistency of the instrument at 0.86. The data collection instrument for the study was administered with the help of four research assistants.

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents Responses on the Extent to which Welding and fabrication Teaching Personnel’s competence at the Training Centers meet IIW Requirements for vocational skill and economic development of the Niger Delta region

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	SD	Remarks
1.	Theories are taught by welding teachers.	1.34	0.89	VLE
2.	Practical are taught by welding instructors.	2.39	0.97	LE
3.	Theory is taught by certified welding technologist.	1.16	0.88	VLE
4.	Personnel with certified International Welder are involved in teaching practical.	1.08	0.95	VLE
5.	Welding teachers demonstrate competence during teaching- learning activities.	2.26	0.94	LE
6.	Welding teachers show good communication skills	3.14	0.96	HE
7.	Welding teachers bring to bear industrial field experience during teaching.	3.12	0.86	HE
Cluster Mean		2.07	0.92	LE

Result in Table 1 revealed that items 6-7 had their mean values ranged from 3.14 - 3.12, which shows that, the extent to which welding and fabrication teaching personnel competence at the training centers meet IIW requirements for vocational skill and economic development of the Niger Delta region is high. Meanwhile, items 2 and 5 had their mean values ranged from 2.39 - 2.26, indicating that, the extent to which welding and fabrication teaching personnel competence

The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. The real limit of numbers was the decision rule for the research question. This is classified under the following levels; Very High Extent: 3.50 – 4.00, High Extent: 2.50 – 3.49, Low Extent: 1.50 - 2.49, and Very Low Extent: 1.00 – 1.49. The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to test the null hypotheses (HO₁) at 0.05 alpha levels of significance. The HO₁ was accepted for items whose test results show that the probability value (p-value) is greater than or equal to the alpha value or the level of significance (0.05), while the null hypotheses of items whose p-value are less than 0.05 (alpha value) were rejected.

RESULTS

The presentation and analysis of data was based on the research questions and hypothesis that guided the study.

Research Question

RQ₁: To what extent does welding and fabrication teaching personnel’s competence at government interventionist training centers meet IIW requirements for vocational skills and economic development of the Niger Delta region?

In order to answer this RQ₁, seven items were generated and presented to the respondents and the data obtained are presented in Table 1.

meet the IIW requirements is low. Items 1, 3 and 4 had their mean values ranged from 1.08-1.34, showing, that the extent to which welding and fabrication teaching personnel competence meet the IIW requirements is very low. Generally, the seven items had a cluster mean value of 2.07; indicating that, the extent to which welding and fabrication teaching personnel competence at the training centers meet IIW requirements for vocational skill and economic development of the Niger Delta

region is low. Table 1 also revealed that the standard deviation of the seven items ranged from 0.86 – 0.97; showing that the respondents were not too far from the mean and from the opinion of one another in their responses.

Test of Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of the respondents on the extent to which welding and fabrication teaching personnel’s competence at government interventionist training centers meet IIW requirements for vocational skill and economic development of the Niger Delta region.

Table 2: Analysis of Variance of the Significant Difference in the mean responses of HTC, WTP and Trainees on the Extent to which Welding and fabrication Teaching Personnel competence at the Training Centers meet IIW Requirements in Niger Delta Region

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	0.631	2	0.315	2.732	0.097
Within Groups	31.276	271	0.115		
Total	31.907	273			

Table 2 shows the ANOVA result of the significant difference in the mean responses of HTC, WTP and Trainees on the extent to which welding and fabrication teaching personnel’s competence at government interventionist training centers meet IIW requirements. The result shows that an F-ratio of 2.73 was obtained with a significant value of 0.097. Since the significant value of 0.097 is greater than 0.05 level of significant, the null hypothesis was accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the mean responses of HTC, WTP and Trainees on the extent to which welding and fabrication teaching personnel’s competence at government interventionist training centers meet IIW requirements for vocational skill and economic development of the Niger Delta region.

Findings and Discussion of the Study

The following were the findings of the study based on the analyzed data and tested RQ₁. It was found that to a very low extent theories are taught by welding teachers; personnel with certified International welding technologist are involved in teaching of theory at the center; and the personnel with certified international welder are involved in teaching practical. Again, the study indicated that to a low extent practical is taught by welding instructors; and welding teachers demonstrates competence during teaching- learning activities. Also, the study shows that to a high extent welding teachers show good communication skills; and they bring to bear industrial field experience during teaching.

The H₀ on no significant difference in the mean responses of HTC, WTP, and Trainees on extent welding teaching personnel at the training centers meet IIW requirements. It shows that the null hypothesis stands

accepted meaning that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of the respondents on the extent to which welding teaching personnel at the training centers meet IIW requirements.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concludes that the welding and fabrication teaching personnel meets IIW requirements for vocational skill and economic development of the Niger Delta region to a low extent, and therefore, they are not competent enough to drive the required socio-economic wellbeing of the region. Hence, the following recommendations are made: (a.) Welding teaching personnel who meet some of the requirement, should be sponsored for relevant training to make up in areas of deficiency by the responsible Government interventionist agency in this case NDDC; (b.) Workshops and seminars on the need for the program to be run in line with IIW standards and requirements for vocational skill and economic development of the Niger Delta region should be jointly organized by NDDC, NIW, Heads of training centers and welding teaching personnel.

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